

The hydrophilid larva consumed up to 6.7 fifth-instar caseworm larvae daily, but only 2-3 of first- or second-instar larvae. Regardless of age, the dytiscid preferred older prey. It was also more voracious, consuming more than 11

fifth-instar caseworm larvae daily.

Aquatic predators may explain why caseworm is more prevalent in rainfed than in irrigated wetlands. Rice irrigated from rivers, reservoirs, or canals would already contain dytiscids

and hydrophilids. Delayed dispersal flights of predators to rainfed fields could allow greater survival of the caseworm, which attacks a young crop before the aquatic predators can initiate a new infestation. *S*

Major insect pests of rice in Cuba

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Rice planthopper *Sogatodes orizicola*, the hoja blanca virus vector, is the principal insect pest of rice in Cuba (see table). Life cycle of adult males is 14-24 d; that of females, 27-31 d. The cycle from egg to adult is about 25 d. *S. orizicola* needs high temperatures (25-27°C) for optimum development.

Higher insect activity and population densities are Apr-Nov.

The most difficult insect pest to control is the rice water weevil, with a 50-d cycle from oviposition to adult emergence. Adults live an average 714 d. *Lissorhoptrus brevirostris* population is highest in Apr-Nov, with large damages to ricefields.

Other important pests are rice stink bug *Oebalus insularis* and fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda*.

Other insects are sporadic pests of rice in Cuba. *S*

First meiotic chromosomes of male *Nephotettix malayanus*

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During growth phase of spermatogenesis in the green leafhopper *N. malayanus*, the primary spermatocytes undergo the first meiotic division. At diakinesis (Fig. 1a), the maximum condensation and coiling of holokinetic chromosomes results in 6 synapsed homologs plus a univalent X-body.

The male *N. malayanus* therefore has the normal diploid complement, $2n = 13$ ($6I_A + X$). The prospective haploid sperm cells are of two types: ($6I_A + X$) and ($6I_A$). The darkly stained, unpaired X-chromosome measured 1.18μ in length and width, and was usually isolated from the bivalent autosomes.

In pachytene analysis of meiotic chromosomes, the mean total

Major insect pests of lowland rice in Cuba, 1976-84.

Scientific name	Growth stage	Damage	Infestation (%)
<i>Sogatodes orizicola</i> (Muir) (Homoptera: Delphacidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	2-12
<i>Sogatodes cubanus</i> (Crawford) (Homoptera: Delphacidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Lissorhoptrus brevirostris</i> (Suffr.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Root feeding (larvae) Leaf feeding on leaves (adults)	10-28
<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> (F. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf feeding (larvae) May eat entire plant	6-10
<i>Hortensia similis</i> (Walk.) (Homoptera: Cicadellidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Draeculacephala cubana</i> (M & B) (Homoptera: Cicadellidae)	Emergence to maximum tillering	Leaf sucking (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Hydrellia</i> sp. (Diptera: Ephydriidae)	Emergence to panicle initiation	Feeding on tissue along the inner margins of emerging leaves (larvae)	New pests
<i>Diatraea saccharalis</i> (F.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae)	Emergence to panicle initiation	Feeding within the stem, severing the vascular system (larvae)	
<i>Caulopsis cuspidatus</i> (Scud.) (Orthoptera: Acrididae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Feeding on the leaf blade	
<i>Conocephalus</i> [= <i>Xiphidium</i>] <i>fasciatus</i> (De Geer) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Leaf feeding (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Conocephaloides obscurelus</i> (De Geer) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Leaf feeding (nymphs and adults)	
<i>Schistocerca pallens</i> (Thunb.) (Orthoptera: Acrididae)	Panicle initiation to heading	Defoliate plants	
<i>Oebalus insularis</i> (Stal) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae)	Milk stage	Sucking each grain (nymphs and adults)	3-17

1. Chromosomes of male *N. malayanus* at a) diakinesis showing $2n = 13$, and b) metaphase I. Spontaneous aberration may result in c) an agmatoploid cell with $2n = 19$ ($9II + X$). IRRI, 1985-86. Arrow indicates the sex chromosome. Magnification 1500X (oil immersion).